

To Study the Amount of Deformity Correction Attained after Pre and Post Operative Total Knee Replacement

Aravind U R¹, K Kumaran Chettiar², Jacob Mathew³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, Kerala.

²Additional Professor Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Konni, Kerala.

³Professor Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, Kerala.

Received: 28-11-2022 / Revised: 30-12-2022 / Accepted: 11-01-2023

Corresponding author: Dr K Kumaran Chettiar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Total knee arthroplasty, another name for total knee replacement, is a surgical treatment used to replace the weight-bearing surfaces of the knee joint in an effort to reduce pain and impairment. It is performed for arthritic knees, which can be brought on by a variety of secondary factors in addition to basic osteoarthritis. Surgery may be riskier and more difficult for individuals who have significant deformities brought on by advanced rheumatoid arthritis, trauma, or osteoarthritis. In order to treat osteoarthritis in the knee, total knee replacement is increasingly performed on senior patients. But if not planned appropriately, a lot of procedures might fail early. The mechanical and anatomical angles of the tibia and femur must be calculated for planning purposes. In this study, calculations of such angles are made. In this study, calculations of these angles are made, and the results are compared to normal values gleaned from several earlier investigations. This shows that the mechanical alignment of the knee may not always need to be corrected in order to rectify the anatomical alignment of the distal femur and proximal tibia. As a result, the mechanical alignment of the anatomically aligned knee is not necessary, and further testing is required to determine the ideal alignment for total knee replacement patients. This necessitates long-term follow-up research.

Keywords: Total Knee Replacement, Osteoarthritis, Valgus, Varus.

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Introduction

One of the most common and incapacitating chronic diseases affecting elderly adults is osteoarthritis (OA). A serious public health issue is the high prevalence of OA in older individuals and women, as well as its moderate to severe effects on day-to-day activities [1]. Total knee replacement (TKR), which is regarded as an efficient technique, has a well-established place in the

management of knee osteoarthritis. Osteoarthritis (OA), rheumatoid arthritis (RA), juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, post-traumatic arthritis, or secondary osteoarthritis, and various forms of inflammatory arthritis are some of the primary causes of arthritis of the knee [2,3]. Total knee arthroplasty (TKA), sometimes known as total knee replacement (TKR), is a

popular orthopaedic procedure in which the articular surfaces (tibial plateau and femoral condyles) of the knee joint are replaced with smooth metal and highly cross-linked polyethylene plastic. By lowering pain and enhancing function, TKR seeks to improve the quality of life of people with end-stage osteoarthritis and has been shown to increase patients' participation in sports and physical activities. In affluent nations, the number of TKR procedures has increased, with younger patients undergoing TKR [4].

Over the past three decades, the number of total knee replacements has rapidly climbed. Total knee replacement surgery can have side effects such as infection, loosening, instability, wear, osteolysis, and periprosthetic fracture, just like any other operation. This might necessitate a second knee replacement operation. The majority of mistakes are the result of the surgeon's poor planning and poor procedures. Therefore, a thorough preoperative assessment and planning are crucial for several surgical processes, such as optimising implant position and soft tissue balancing, in order to limit the likelihood of surgical failure and the necessity for any subsequent total knee replacements.

The postoperative evaluation aids the physician in identifying surgical mistakes and enhancing outcomes in subsequent operations. A key component of total knee replacement is the correction of coronal plane deformity, such as valgus or varus. The most accurate way to determine these anomalies is to measure the lower limb's biomechanical axis using a hip to ankle three joint weight bearing xray [5]

Preoperative and postoperative 3 joint weight-bearing x-rays of the hip, knee, and ankle are helpful in determining the degree of correction achieved by surgery by calculating the mechanical angle, which determines the degree of varus or valgus correction. The mechanical axis of the femur and mechanical

axis of the tibia together make up the hip, knee, and ankle angle. A line connecting the femur's head's centre and its intercondylar notch is the femur's mechanical axis [6]. This study aims to examine the lower limb's mechanical and anatomical axis both before and after surgery.

Materials and Method

This study was conducted from Sep 2020 to Dec 2021. During this period 108 cases of adult patients who underwent total knee replacement at Government Medical College Kozhikode were selected

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty for primary osteoarthritis of knee during the study period.
- Age between 50 – 90 years.
- Patients willing to give written and informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Age less than 50
- Age greater than 90,
- Secondary osteoarthritis
- Revision total knee arthroplasty
- Flexion deformity of the knee of more than 10 degrees.
- Limb length discrepancy
- Associated hip / ankle deformity

The institutional ethics committee gave its clearance for the project. A preoperative hip knee ankle weight-bearing x-ray is taken of an arthritic patient whose knee is scheduled for surgery, and the hip knee ankle angle, distal femoral anatomical angle, proximal tibial anatomical angle, and femorotibial angle are all measured.

The angle between the femoral notch's (the mechanical axis of the femur) midpoint and the line connecting it to the ankle joint's midway is known as the hip-knee-ankle angle

(mechanical axis of the tibia). The anatomical axes of the femur and the tibia comes together to generate the femorotibial angle. The joint line of the femur passing through the distal aspect of both condyles and the anatomical axis of the femur produce the angle known as the anatomical angle of the femur. The anatomical angle of the tibia is the angle created by the joint line of the tibia passing through the tibial plateau and the tibial axis.

Observation and Results

In all 108 patients studied, the indication for surgery was primary osteoarthritis knee, of which 88 patients had their first total knee replacement, while the remaining 20 had their second. Revision cases were excluded. Total of 108 patients included a range from 50 years to 78 years. Mean age was 64.13 with a standard deviation of 7.825 years. Out of 108, females constituted 59.3% (64), and men 40.7% (44). The side done was almost similar, with right side being done in 51.9 percent (56) and left side done in 48.1 percent (52).

The preoperative x-rays of knees were used to classify the grade of osteoarthritis using IKDC (International Knee Documentation Committee) classification. There was no case belonging to grade 1. Grade 4 had the maximum case, 52(48.1%). Grade 2 and 3 had 18 (16.7%) and 38(35.2%) cases respectively. Hip knee ankle angles were measured both preoperatively and postoperatively. The mean angle preoperatively was 170.1 degrees, with a standard deviation of 14.1 degrees, which indicates that most of the cases studied, were of varus deformity.

Preoperatively HKA angle ranged between 129.5 degrees and 201 degrees. Postoperative mean HKA angle was 177 degrees with a standard deviation of 5.1 degrees. This indicates that postoperative alignment was mostly either in near neutral or in varus. It ranged from 164.5 degrees to 191.6 degrees.

When considering the alignment with reference to previous studies, preoperatively 80 cases (74.1%) were in varus, 24 cases (22.2%) were in valgus and only 4 cases (3.7%) were in neutral position. But postoperatively the number of neutrally aligned knees went up to 42 cases (38.9%) from 4 cases. But majority of cases were in varus, 52 cases (48.1%) and 14 cases (13%) in valgus. DFA (Distal femoral anatomical) angle in preoperative patients were predominantly neutral, i.e. 49 cases (45.4%), with 45 cases (41.7%) in valgus and 14 cases (13%) in varus.

FFC alignment (postoperative distal femoral anatomical alignment) in post total knee replacement patients were mostly normal, 82 cases (75.9%) with 14 cases in valgus (13%) and 12 cases (11.1%) in varus. Following surgery distal femoral angle changed to a maximum of 10.6 degrees varus and 11.1-degree valgus with a mean change of 1.2 degrees with a standard deviation of 4.12 degrees.

Postoperatively 85 cases were neutrally aligned with the others ranging between 2.8-degree varus to 6.5-degree valgus with a standard deviation of 1.5 degrees. Preoperatively Proximal tibial anatomical angle (beta angle) ranged from 16 degrees varus to 12.6 degrees valgus with a mean angle of 4 degrees varus with a standard deviation of 4.9 degrees. Frontal Tibial Component angle (postoperative) ranged between 7.8 degrees varus to 2.9-degree valgus with a mean angle of 1.3 degrees varus with a standard deviation of 2.2 degrees. Preoperative Proximal Tibial Anatomical angle (beta angle) was predominantly in varus 64 cases (59.3%), 15 cases (13.9%) in valgus and 29 cases (26.9%) in neutral alignment. Postoperatively 71 cases (65.7%) had a neutrally aligned proximal tibial anatomical angle, while 19 cases (17.6 %) were in valgus and 18 cases (16.7%) were in varus.

Discussion

The study included 108 patients, with a mean age of 64 ± 7.8 with females (59%) predominating the study. The sides were almost equal. There was a significantly strong correlation between mechanical and anatomical angles of the lower limb both preoperatively and postoperatively. The mean mechanical angle of the knee was 170.1 ± 14.1 preoperatively and 177.2 ± 5.1 postoperatively. The mean anatomical angle was 182.4 ± 13.4 preoperatively and 175.5 ± 4.3 postoperatively. The mean preoperative alpha angle was 96.2 ± 4 degrees, while the mean Frontal Femoral Component angle was 95.1 ± 2.9 degrees. The mean preoperative beta angle was 86 ± 4.9 degrees, while the mean Frontal Tibial Component angle was 88.7 ± 2.2 degrees.

The mean anatomical angle was 182.4 ± 13.4 preoperatively and 175.5 ± 4.3 postoperatively. Calculating from it (360 - FT angle) the medial anatomical angle is 177.8 ± 13.4 preoperatively and 184.5 ± 4.3 postoperatively. Therefore, the mean difference between the Mechanical and anatomical angles of the lower limb is 7.5 ± 1.4 degrees. Michael H Oswald *et al* [7] in their study showed a difference of 6 degrees. It is much different from the value obtained as per the study of William Paul Gielis *et al* [8] which was nearly 2.18 degrees, done in the Netherlands in a random population above 40 years. Turkish study by Deniz Evcik *et al* [9] showed the value as 4.9 ± 1.7 degrees.

Conclusion

For both preoperative and postoperative assessment of total knee replacement, a three joint hip-knee-ankle weight bearing x-ray is crucial. Prior to and following surgery, the mechanical and anatomical axes must be assessed for improved diagnosis and results. Total knee replacement can return the

mechanical and anatomical angles of the knee to zero or a number very close to zero.

The mechanical and anatomical knee angles are significantly correlated. For the examination of anatomical axis alignment of each component postoperatively, frontal femoral component angle and frontal tibial component angle must be measured.

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